

Argument-based intervention as a way to reduce covid-19 unfounded beliefs and vaccination hesitancy

Peter Teličák, Jakub Šrol & Peter Halama

Institute of Experimental psychology, Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences, Slovak

Academy of Sciences

peter.telicak@savba.sk, jakub.srol@savba.sk, peter.halama@savba.sk

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Corresponding author: Peter Teličák, Institute of Experimental psychology, Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta 9, Bratislava, Slovak Republic. E-mail: peter.telicak@savba.sk

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Abstract

The aim of the experimental study was to verify the reduction of Covid-19 unfounded beliefs through arguments in favor of vaccination. The sample includes 720 participants recruited by Qualtrics (50% women, age: $M = 38.8$, $SD = 10.90$). The participants were equally and randomly divided into three groups. The control group was given the task of reading a neutral text about Norway. The first experimental group was provided with a debunking text that corrected popular misinformation and unfounded beliefs about vaccination against polio and vaccination against Covid-19. The second experimental group read the same text as the first, with two additional paragraphs addressing the motives and errors in the thinking of unfounded belief spreaders. The results confirmed that exposing the participants to arguments for vaccination reduces the endorsement of Covid-19 unfounded beliefs and increases the willingness to be vaccinated against Covid-19 disease.

Keywords: anti-vaccination attitudes; intervention; conspiracy beliefs; pseudoscientific beliefs; Covid-19

INTRODUCTION

Negative attitudes toward vaccination can be traced back to 1796 when Edward Jenner attempted to develop a vaccine against smallpox (Stern & Markel, 2005), which started a gradual momentum of opposition to vaccination (Wolfe et al., 2002). In modern history, one of the key moments for the anti-vaccination movement was the year 1998, when Andrew Wakefield published a study in the *Lancet* to prove the link between measles vaccination and autism (Wakefield et al., 1998). As we now know, the results of the study were falsified, presumably because of a competing financial interest, and the study itself was eventually retracted (Rao & Andrade, 2011). Nevertheless, the study shook confidence in vaccination among some parts of a population, resulting in the emergence of various unfounded beliefs about vaccination that led to a rise in vaccination refusals (Eggertson, 2010).

Today, anti-vax attitudes and associated unfounded beliefs are also coming to the fore (Jolley & Douglas, 2014, 2017; Burki, 2020; Sturm & Albrecht, 2021; Roberts et al., 2022). These types of beliefs undermine information about the benefits of vaccination and point to the alleged negative side effects of vaccination ignored by pharmaceutical companies to maximalize their financial profits, or even to harm the people intentionally (Kata, 2010). As these beliefs have a range of negative effects on health-related attitudes (Jolley & Douglas, 2017; Johnson et al., 2020; Allington et al., 2020), it is important to study how we can reduce the level of unfounded beliefs and anti-vax attitudes (Curiel & Ramírez, 2021). This issue became even more relevant since the global push for vaccination against COVID-19, as we have witnessed a resurgence of anti-vaccination attitudes and vaccine hesitancy, both of which have been consistently linked to the endorsement of unfounded beliefs and subsequent impact on health behaviour (for a review, see van Mulukom et al., 2022).

To address this issue in the present study, we tested the effectiveness of two argument-based interventions (based on Stojanov, 2015) in reducing conspiracy and pseudoscientific

beliefs about vaccination against COVID-19 and increasing vaccination intentions. Before we introduce our experimental design in more detail, we summarize previous research aimed at reducing unfounded beliefs about vaccination and increasing vaccination intentions, and mention some of the key psychological predictors of beliefs in this domain, which we controlled for when examining the effectiveness of our two interventions.

Interventions aimed at reducing unfounded beliefs about vaccines or vaccine hesitancy

Previous studies identified several ways to reduce anti-vaccination attitudes. The most common approaches to reduce false anti-vaccination claims and other misinformation are two-fold (e.g. Jolley & Douglas, 2017; Ecker et al., 2022). The first is to provide people with a more general preemptive message that should help them recognize subsequently encountered misinformation (prebunking) and the second is responding to specific misinformation after they were encountered and emphasize why they are incorrect (debunking). There is an ongoing debate about the relative effectiveness of these two approaches (e.g. Ecker et al., 2022). For example, while a study by Jolley and Douglas (2014) found that exposure to arguments in favor of vaccination reduces the propensity to hold anti-vaccination beliefs (see also Stojanov, 2015), a later research by the authors suggested that presenting arguments against vaccine conspiracy theories increases vaccination intentions only if these arguments are presented before people are exposed to conspiracy theories (Jolley & Douglas, 2017). In our study, we aimed at debunking unfounded beliefs about vaccines which were already prevalent at the time of experiment, therefore we constructed two debunking interventions based on the two most common ways to combat misinformation. The first is providing a corrective account that addresses falsehoods in the misinformation and the second providing an account that highlights the logical fallacies that are commonly used when spreading certain type of misinformation (e.g. Ecker et al., 2022; Schmid & Betsch, 2019).

Importantly, we were interested not only in whether these two debunking interventions will work to reduce people's unfounded beliefs about vaccines but also in how they increase their vaccination intentions. This is important because previous studies did suggest that even after corrections, misinformation can still influence people's beliefs, which has been dubbed the continued influence effect (Ecker et al., 2022; Walter & Tukachinsky, 2020). Indeed, study by Stojanov (2015), which served as an inspiration for our research, suggested that while unfounded health beliefs can be reduced by arguments that critically refute unfounded beliefs about vaccination, this did not increase people's willingness to vaccinate. A study by Nyhan et al. (2014) even suggested that correcting misperception about MMR vaccine actually caused decreased intentions to vaccinate among some parents. Therefore, even though there is a large body of evidence showing that debunking strategies are effective in countering misinformation (Chan et al., 2017; Walter & Murphy, 2018), it is much less clear whether and among whom the reduction of unfounded beliefs (about vaccines against Covid-19, in our case) actually results in improved vaccination intentions.

To examine this even further, our study included several key covariates to help us examine whether our debunking interventions are effective among people with different levels of pre-existing unfounded beliefs, trust, and analytic thinking. These three covariates were selected based in extant literature showing their associations with unfounded beliefs about Covid-19 (for a review, see van Mulukom et al., 2022). Specifically, we included analytic thinking because it has been previously shown to negatively correlate with anti-vaccination attitudes and both Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs and more generic health-related unfounded beliefs, although not with vaccination intentions (Čavojová et al., 2022, 2023). Likewise, lower trust – in authorities but also interpersonal trust – has been shown to be consistently correlated with the endorsement of unfounded beliefs about Covid-19 (van Mulukom et al., 2022), which is why we included a generic measure of trust in our study. Finally, since perhaps the strongest

predictor of whether people believe unfounded beliefs about Covid-19 was their belief in more generic conspiracy and pseudoscientific claims (e.g. Šrol et al., 2021) or generic conspiracy motives (Georgiou et al., 2020), we measured participants' conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs and conspiracy mentality prior to the experimental manipulation and included these variables as covariates when testing the effectiveness of our debunking interventions.

The present study

The aim of the present experimental study was to test whether we can effectively reduce people's unfounded beliefs about vaccination against COVID-19 and increase their vaccination intentions using interventions based on the arguments in favor of vaccination (Diep, 2013; Stojanov, 2015; Walter & Tukachinsky, 2020). The interventions included a simple debunking text which exposed various unfounded beliefs about vaccines and a more specific text focusing on the fallacious arguments presented by those who spread unfounded beliefs about vaccines. Both of these interventions were based on a previous study by Stojanov (2015), but adapted to not only include text debunking unfounded beliefs about vaccines in general, but also some specific examples related to vaccines against COVID-19. Afterward, we measured participants' trust in doctors and scientists, vaccination intentions, and conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs about COVID-19 to see whether the interventions were effective. Moreover, to demonstrate the robustness of the potential intervention effects, we controlled for potential differences in analytic thinking, conspiracy mentality, general trust, and unfounded beliefs about COVID-19 that were measured prior to the experimental manipulation.

METHOD

Participants

The statistical program G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007) was used to determine the minimum sample size. Using the ANOVA method to measure differences between groups and with effect

size $f > .15$, statistical power $(1 - \beta) .95$, and level $\alpha = .05$, the minimum sample size was set at 690 participants. The research sample consisted of participants recruited through an external research agency (DataCollect) that recruited a quota sample representative of Slovak population in terms of gender, age, and education level distribution. The resulting number of participants who took part in our experiment conducted via online survey created in Qualtrics was 720 (360 women, 360 men), aged 18 to 61 years ($M = 38.8$, $SD = 10.9$). For the experiment, participants were randomly divided into three groups. The demographic distributions for the three experimental groups are provided in the Section B of the Supplementary material. Participants were informed in an understandable manner about the aims and purpose of the study and how the data obtained would be handled. No information was requested from participants that was not in accordance with ethical standards. The design of the experimental study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Slovak Academy of Science.

Materials

The descriptive statistics and internal consistency coefficients of the all materials in the present study are presented in Table 1 below.

Dependent measures – vaccination intentions and trust:

Four items were used to measure whether our experimental manipulation was effective in positively affecting participants' vaccination intentions and trust in scientists and doctors. Participants responded to these four items using a scale from 1 (“definitely not”) to 5 (“definitely yes”).

Covid-19 vaccination recommendation. We measured the participant's willingness to recommend vaccination against the Covid-19 disease to their immediate family and acquaintances with the following item: *“Would you recommend getting vaccinated against the Covid-19 vaccine to your immediate family and acquaintances?”*

Fictitious child vaccination intention. Similarly as in a study by Stojanov (2015), we also asked out participants to imagine that they were the parent of a fictitious child who needed to be

vaccinated against polio the following day. The item was formulated: *"Imagine that you are the parent of a healthy three-month-old Marek, who was summoned by his doctor for polio vaccination. Would you have Marek vaccinated?"*

Trust in scientists and doctors. We measured the participant's trust in scientists and doctors with the following two items: *"Do you trust scientists?"* and *"Do you trust doctors?"*

Dependent measures – pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs about Covid-19:

The Covid-19 Unfounded Beliefs Scale (Teličák & Halama, 2022) was used to measure conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs. The scale contains 15 items divided into three dimensions measuring: pseudoscientific beliefs related to the containment measures (five items; e.g. *"The test for the presence of COVID-19 is dangerous and harmful to health"*), pseudoscientific beliefs related to the treatment (four items; e.g. *"Homeopathic treatment of COVID -19 is more effective compared to the classical form of treatment"*) and conspiracy beliefs (six items; e.g. *"The COVID-19 pandemic was planned by economic powers"*). Participants responded to all items using a scale from 1 (*"strongly disagree"*) to 5 (*"strongly agree"*).

Control measures:

These measures of trust, analytic thinking, and conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs were administered at the beginning of the study to determine whether our three groups did not differ significantly before introducing our experimental manipulation. With the exception of the Cognitive reflection test, participants responded to all items in this section using a scale from 1 (*"strongly disagree"*) to 5 (*"strongly agree"*). We opted for using different measurement instruments in the pre-test in comparison with the post-test measurement so as not to expose our participants to the exactly same measures twice as we believed this could affect their responses. Therefore, we generally opted for using more generic measures in the pre-test (see below) as these were very likely to give us good indication whether our three experimental groups differ significantly in the main concepts measured in the present study before the experimental manipulation. Besides the aforementioned materials, our survey included several methods (Dark Tetrad personality variables and social well-being) which were part of another research project and therefore, these measures are not presented or analyzed here.

Trust was measured using the six-item General Trust Scale (Yamagishi & Yamagishi, 1994; Jasielska et al., 2021; example item: "*Most people are basically honest*").

Analytic thinking. We used the original Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT; Frederick, 2005) to measure analytic thinking. It contains three math problems with compelling but wrong intuitive answers (e.g. "*If it takes 3 people 3 hours to make 3 things, how long would it take 10 people to make 10 things?*", intuitive answer: 10 hours, correct answer: 3 hours). The number of correct responses to these three items was used as an index of analytic thinking. The CRT was originally thought to measure primarily numerical reasoning ability (Welsh et al., 2013). However, it was later recognized that the performance on CRT relates to a range of concepts outside the numerical domain, such as moral judgements, religious belief, and belief in various unfounded claims, which is why it has been conceptualized by some as a measure of a more general tendency to think analytically and to suppress compelling intuitions (Pennycook et al., 2015). It is now widely used as a measure of analytic thinking and has been shown repeatedly to be negatively associated with unfounded pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs about COVID-19 (e.g. van Mulukom et al., 2023).

Conspiracy mentality was measured using the Conspiracy Mentality Questionnaire (CMQ; Bruder et al., 2013). The questionnaire contains 5 items, such as "*I think that there are secret organizations that greatly influence political decisions*".

Conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs about Covid-19. Specific conspiracy (e.g. "*There are medicines for the disease Covid-19, but certain groups of people keep them secret*") and pseudoscientific beliefs (e.g. "*52% alcohol is already a proven medicine against COVID-19*") regarding the Covid-19 pandemic were in the pre-test measured by nine items (five for conspiracy, four for pseudoscientific beliefs). Please, note that these items were different from the ones used to measure Covid-19 conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs in the post-test measurement.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics and internal consistency estimates for the materials in the present study

Control group (N = 240)							
	M	Mdn	SD	SKE	KUR	α	ω
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (measures)	2.36	2.20	1.13	0.38	-1.02	0.87	0.88
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (treatment)	2.45	2.50	0.96	-0.02	-0.85	0.84	0.84
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs	2.90	3.00	1.31	-0.06	-1.27	0.96	0.96
Conspiracy mentality (pretest)	3.61	3.60	0.82	-0.40	0.08	0.82	0.83
Covid-19 conspiracy (pretest)	2.33	2.20	1.12	0.69	-0.47	0.89	0.89
Covid-19 pseudoscientific (pretest)	2.13	2.00	0.92	0.64	-0.17	0.74	0.75
Trust (pretest)	3.27	3.33	0.69	-0.19	-0.49	0.77	0.79
Analytic thinking (pretest)	0.36	0.33	0.37	0.54	-1.12	0.67	0.67
Vaccination child intention	4.34	5.00	1.15	-0.19	2.11		
Vaccination recommendation	3.05	3.00	1.66	-0.05	-1.61		
Trust doctors	3.70	4.00	1.11	-0.66	-0.10		
Trust scientists	3.73	4.00	1.12	-0.70	-0.05		
Experimental group 1 (N = 241)							
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (measures)	2.10	1.80	1.12	0.78	-0.54	0.89	0.90
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (treatment)	2.30	2.25	0.93	0.07	-1.13	0.82	0.83
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs	2.61	2.67	1.28	0.23	-1.20	0.95	0.95
Conspiracy mentality (pretest)	3.61	3.60	0.82	-0.52	0.05	0.83	0.83
Covid-19 conspiracy (pretest)	2.15	1.80	1.08	0.84	-0.20	0.89	0.90
Covid-19 pseudoscientific (pretest)	1.99	1.75	0.99	0.86	0.01	0.82	0.83
Trust (pretest)	3.34	3.33	0.69	-0.31	-0.46	0.76	0.77
Analytic thinking (pretest)	0.40	0.33	0.38	0.39	-1.27	0.69	0.69
Vaccination child intention	4.42	5.00	1.06	-1.96	2.10		
Vaccination recommendation	3.52	4.00	1.59	-0.54	1.28		
Trust doctors	3.79	4.00	1.12	-0.75	-0.14		

Trust scientists	3.91	4.00	1.07	-0.75	-0.20		
Experimental group 2 (N = 239)							
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (measures)	2.01	1.80	1.05	0.99	0.09	0.86	0.88
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs (treatment)	2.26	2.25	0.97	0.33	-0.72	0.85	0.85
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs	2.53	2.50	1.23	0.33	-1.15	0.95	0.95
Conspiracy mentality (pretest)	3.58	3.60	0.79	0.16	-0.32	0.81	0.81
Covid-19 conspiracy (pretest)	2.12	1.80	1.05	0.16	0.03	0.89	0.90
Covid-19 pseudoscientific (pretest)	1.93	1.75	0.95	0.16	0.43	0.78	0.79
Trust (pretest)	3.27	3.33	0.71	0.16	-0.26	0.79	0.80
Analytic thinking (pretest)	0.34	0.33	0.35	0.67	-0.79	0.62	0.64
Vaccination child intention	4.55	5.00	0.89	-2.11	3.65		
Vaccination recommendation	3.71	4.00	1.51	-0.76	-0.91		
Trust doctors	3.90	4.00	0.98	-0.66	0.14		
Trust scientists	4.00	4.00	1.01	-0.91	0.47		

Note. The table shows descriptive statistics - means, medians, standard deviations, and estimates of kurtosis and skewness - and internal consistency estimates (Cronbach's alpha, MacDonald omega) for all materials in the present study separately for the three experimental groups.

Procedure

The whole study was administered in a form of an online study created in Qualtrics. After participants consented to take part in the study, they answered several basic demographic questions (about sex, age and education level). Next, all participants filled several pre-test measures regarding trust, analytic thinking and pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs about the Covid-19 pandemic. Then, participants were randomly split into three groups. The first experimental group was given a debunking text to read, which we obtained from a study on the popularization of science (Diep, 2013) and which was also used in a similar experimental study by Stojanov (2015). The text in question debunks falsehoods about vaccination in general. We slightly modified the text and added information refuting untruths about the Covid-19 vaccine. The text was evaluated by two medicine experts for form and content. The exact wording of this text (along with wordings of the texts used in the other two groups) can be found in Section A in the Supplementary Materials. The second experimental group was given the task of reading

the same text as the first experimental group, but in addition, they read two more paragraphs in which the motives and errors in the thinking of those who spread unfounded beliefs are pointed out (e.g. While it is true that a person may become infected after being vaccinated against Covid-19, it is not because of the vaccination, but rather, for example, because they have met a person who has the disease). We took the text used by Stojanov (2015) and modified it with information about vaccination against Covid-19 disease. In comparison, the control group read a neutral text about the country Norway, which we took from Wikipedia (2022) and which was similar in length to the text presented to the first experimental group. The control text about Norway was chosen at random with our only condition being that it did not explicitly conflict with the experimental theme. The reading duration for the control group was up to 3 minutes, similar to the first experimental group, which was also 3 minutes. The second experimental group took up to 4.5 minutes to read the text. After reading their respective texts, participants in all three groups proceeded to fill in the materials regarding vaccination intentions and trust in doctors and scientists. Finally, all participants filled in a questionnaire measuring pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs about Covid-19. The scheme of the experimental procedure is indicated in the Section C of the Supplementary material.

Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS, R-Studio, and Jamovi programs. We performed descriptive analysis and used skewness and kurtosis as a reference frame for assessing the normality of the data distribution (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). To assess the internal consistency of the scales and subscales, we used Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega. One-way analysis of variance was used to test for the presence of differences between groups. Homogeneity of variances was tested using Levene's test. If the assumptions for equality of variances were not met, the Welch correction to ANOVA was applied. The Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc pairwise comparisons were used to test the differences between the pairs of groups. Data file for analyses performed in the study are publicly available at https://osf.io/h2eb3/?view_only=c6396b0beb7c45e18b265dea32fa8d09

RESULTS

Differences between groups in pre-test measurements

First, we conducted a series of ANOVAs to examine whether there were any differences between the three experimental groups in the pre-test measurements regarding analytic thinking, trust, conspiracy mentality, and conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs about Covid-

19. As can be seen from Table 2, there were no significant differences in any of the variables between the three groups. However, it should be noted that the participants in the control group had slightly higher endorsement of Covid-19 pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs than the other two experimental groups, as indicated by marginally significant results of the analyses of variance. For this reason, we also recalculated the results below while controlling for the potential differences in these variables to see whether the same patterns of results hold.

Table 2 Results of analysis-of variance for the differences between the experimental groups in the pre-test measurements

	group	M	SD	F	df	p
Conspiracy mentality	control	3.61	0.82	0.128	717	.88
	experimental 1	3.61	0.83			
	experimental 2	3.58	0.79			
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs	control	2.33	1.12	2.553	717	.08
	experimental 1	2.15	1.08			
	experimental 2	2.12	1.05			
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs	control	2.13	0.92	2.769	717	.06
	experimental 1	1.99	0.99			
	experimental 2	1.93	0.95			
Trust	control	3.27	0.69	0.852	717	.43
	experimental 1	3.34	0.69			
	experimental 2	3.27	0.71			
Analytic thinking	control	0.36	0.37	2.180	418*	.11
	experimental 1	0.41	0.38			
	experimental 2	0.34	0.35			

Note. The table shows the results of a one-way analysis of variance for differences in pre-test measurements among the three experimental groups, along with the descriptive statistics in each of the groups. * Welch's correction

Differences between groups in post-test measurements

Next, we tested for potential differences between the three experimental groups in the post-test measurements regarding Covid-19 pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs, vaccination intentions and recommendation, and trust in doctors and scientists. As can be seen in Table 3, one-way analyses of variance indicated a significant difference between the groups when it came to four variables: Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs regarding containment measures, Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs, Covid-19 vaccination recommendation, and trust in scientists.

Table 3 Results of analysis-of variance for the differences between the experimental groups in the post-test measurements

	group	M	SD	F	df	p
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs regarding measures	control	2.36	1.13			
	experimental 1	2.10	1.12	6.88	717	<.001
	experimental 2	2.10	1.05			
Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs regarding treatments	control	2.45	0.96			
	experimental 1	2.30	0.93	2.58	717	.08
	experimental 2	2.26	0.97			
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs	control	2.90	1.32			
	experimental 1	2.61	1.28	5.60	717	.004
	experimental 2	2.53	1.23			
Child vaccination intentions	control	4.34	1.15			
	experimental 1	4.42	1.06	2.67	473*	.07
	experimental 2	4.55	0.89			
Covid-19 vaccination recommendation	control	3.50	1.66			
	experimental 1	3.52	1.59	11.30	717	<.001
	experimental 2	3.71	1.51			
Trust in doctors	control	3.70	1.11			
	experimental 1	3.79	1.12	2.11	473*	.12
	experimental 2	3.90	0.98			
Trust in scientists	control	3.73	1.12			
	experimental 1	3.91	1.07	2.80	473*	.023
	experimental 2	4.00	1.01			

Note. The table shows the results of a one-way analysis of variance for differences in post-test measurements among the three experimental groups, along with the descriptive statistics in each of the groups. ANOVAs indicating a significant ($p < .05$) difference between groups are presented in bold. * Welch's correction

In cases where ANOVA indicated a significant difference between the experimental group, we have conducted post-hoc tests with Bonferonni correction (see Table 4 for results). As can be seen from the table, control group reported higher level of Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs and pseudoscientific beliefs regarding measures and lower Covid-19 vaccination recommendation in comparison with the two experimental groups. Participants in control group also had lower trust in scientists than participants in the second experimental groups, but the difference was not significant in case of the first experimental group, which only received argument-based intervention. Other than that, however, there was no significant difference between scores reported by the first and second experimental group, suggesting that providing participants with text about intentions of those who spread unfounded beliefs about vaccination may have little effect over providing basic debunking of arguments used in anti-vaccination narratives. Also, it should be noted that all measured differences were relatively weak, which is not surprising

given the brief nature of the intervention provided to the two experimental groups and the presumable deep-rootedness of the beliefs we were trying to influence.

Table 4 Results of one-factor analysis of variance for post-test after accounting for Bonferroni correction

Covid-19 pseudoscience measures beliefs		dif. M	df	t	p	d
control	experimental1	0.26	717	2.64	.025	0.24
	experimental 2	0.36	717	3.58	<.001	0.33
expermental 1	experimental 2	0.10	717	0.94	1.00	0.09
Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs		dif. M	df	t	p	d
control	experimental1	0.29	717	2.54	.034	0.23
	experimental 2	0.43	717	3.16	.005	0.29
expermental 1	experimental 2	0.08	717	0.62	1.00	0.06
Vaccination against Covid-19		dif. M	df	t	p	d
control	experimental1	0.47	717	-3.29	.003	0.30
	experimental 2	0.66	717	-4.55	<.001	0.42
expermental 1	experimental 2	0.19	717	-1.27	.614	0.12
Trust in scientists		dif. M	df	t	p	d
control	experimental1	0.09	717	-1.84	.198	0.17
	experimental 2	0.20	717	-2.73	.020	0.25
expermental 1	experimental 2	0.11	717	-0.89	1.00	0.08

Additional analyses

To test the robustness of our results, we also examined the potential differences between the three experimental groups in the post-test measurements regarding Covid-19 pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs, vaccination intentions and recommendation, and trust in doctors and scientists while controlling for demographic factors and pre-test measurement using one-way analysis of covariance. As covariates we added the demographic variables (age, education level and gender) and variables from pre-test measurement (trust, analytic thinking, conspiracy mentality, Covid-19 conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs). As can be seen in Section D of the Supplementary material (Table S2), one-way analyses of covariance indicated a significant difference between the groups when it came to three variables: Covid-19 pseudoscientific beliefs regarding containment measures, Covid-19 conspiracy beliefs and Covid-19 vaccination recommendation, but not trust in scientists as can be seen above in Table 4 where are presented the results of one- way analysis of variance. Secondly, for an interested reader, we also present a correlation analysis between all variables separately for the three experimental groups which can be found in Section E of the Supplementary material. As a third step, we conducted moderation analyzes focused on the intervention effect on post hoc variables moderated by demographic variables (age, education level, and gender) and variables from the pre-test

measurement (trust, analytical thinking, conspiracy mentality). However, moderation effects were not evident. The results are in the supplementary materials in Section F in Table 7.

DISCUSSION

The aim of the experimental study was to verify whether unfounded beliefs about vaccination against Covid-19 can be effectively reduced through brief arguments in favor of vaccination. The study also tested whether this intervention would have a positive effect on the willingness to vaccinate one's child against childhood diseases and the willingness to recommend vaccination against Covid-19 to close family and friends, as well as whether it will influence the trust in doctors and scientists. Similarly to some of the previous studies, the intervention was carried out through arguments in favor of vaccination (Diep, 2013; Stojanov, 2015; Walter & Tukachinsky, 2020), but these were adapted to deal specifically with the prevalent unfounded beliefs about Covid-19 vaccination, which were dominant at the time when we conducted the study. Also, the strength of our study lied in fact that prior to the experimental intervention, we examined potential differences between individual groups in cognitive reflection, general trust, conspiracy mentality, and conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs related to the Covid-19 pandemic (different from the ones used in the post-test measurement). This allowed us to test the robustness of the effect of our experimental intervention even while accounting for potential pre-existing differences between groups in these factors. Indeed, the most important finding of our study was that the argument-based intervention had the desired effect – that is, it significantly reduced unfounded beliefs and increased willingness to recommend Covid-19 vaccination in experimental groups – and this effect was present even after accounting for all of the covariates measured in our study.

Despite the brief nature of our argument-based interventions, we managed to demonstrate a significant reduction in the endorsement of COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs and pseudoscientific beliefs related to measures, although the effects were weak. The statistically significant differences observed between the control group and the experimental groups suggest that one way to reduce unfounded beliefs is through the ability to interpret and assess the quality of information using arguments (Stojanov, 2015), which can be facilitated by scientific thinking, shown to be a negative predictor of unfounded beliefs (Čavojová, Šrol, & Ballová Mikušková, 2020; Čavojová, Šrol, & Jurkovič, 2020). Stojanov's (2015) experimental study demonstrated the effect of reducing healthcare-related unfounded beliefs through arguments that critically debunked vaccination-related unfounded beliefs. It appears that the ability to interpret and assess the quality of information can be facilitated by argumentation skills that

enhance cognitive and communication abilities, thus enabling critical evaluation of various information (Kuhn & Dean, 2005). Argumentation skills help evaluate the quality of information and develop critical thinking, which is a negative predictor of unfounded beliefs (Swami et al., 2014; Songsil et al., 2019). For example, exposing individuals to pro-vaccination arguments reduces the tendency to adhere to antivaccine beliefs (Jolley & Douglas, 2014). The results of a meta-analysis (Walter & Tukachinsky, 2020) indicated that corrections of unfounded beliefs through arguments based on scientific facts can subsequently reduce susceptibility to unfounded beliefs. Another important aspect is the process of "demystification" of unfounded beliefs (Guan et al., 2021) which helps decode and clarify the mechanisms behind unfounded beliefs, enabling individuals to understand the purpose of spreading such beliefs. This process could help individuals to recognize the epistemological dishonesty of unfounded beliefs. However, our study's additional results suggest that COVID-19 pseudoscientific beliefs regarding treatment were not reduced after the intervention. A possible explanation could be the partial outdatedness of the items measuring COVID-19 pseudoscientific beliefs related to treatment. The experiment took place in the summer of 2021, while the data collection for the psychometric study on COVID-19 unfounded beliefs (Teličák & Halama, 2022) was conducted in November 2020. In the meantime, new pseudoscientific beliefs emerged about not scientifically tested and thus risky alternative forms of COVID-19 treatment, such as those related to the use of Ivermectin (Pimentel et al., 2020). Since using instruments that are not psychometrically tested is among repeated criticisms of research on belief in unfounded claims, we have opted in our study for using a psychometrically tested scale of Covid-19 unfounded beliefs. This, however, unfortunately meant that some of the most recent pseudoscientific beliefs were not included in our measurement instrument.

Next, we turn to the effects of our experimental interventions on the behavioural intentions regarding vaccination and trust measures. The measurement results regarding the willingness to vaccinate children against polio indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between the individual groups. One interpretation of this finding could be that in Slovakia (formerly Czechoslovakia), regular vaccination against polio (paralytic poliomyelitis) has been common since 1960, and in 1961, the disease was even successfully eradicated from the territory (Rozsypal, 2019). Therefore, people, considering the regularity of polio vaccination (as well as the information and consensus among doctors regarding the vaccination), had the opportunity to develop a predominantly positive attitude towards it, which could also be reflected in the absence of differences in the results of our experiment. Indeed, as can be seen from the descriptive statistics obtained from the control group, the median answer

to this item was actually to definitely vaccinate the child. Therefore, there seemed to have been a ceiling effect on this items which seems to explain why we weren't able to increase the willingness of participants to vaccinate a fictitious child anymore using our interventions. One potential limitation of this part of study is that we asked all participants to imagine that they were the parents of a three-month-old child in an attempt to phrase the question uniformly for all participants, without considering whether they were actually parents.

The same was not true with regard to the other behavioural intention item which dealt with the willingness to recommend Covid-19 vaccine in which the answers were much more variable in the control group. In comparison with polio, which has been around for a long time, the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic created a new situation in which it was necessary to urgently find a way to eliminate the adverse effects of the SARS-CoV-2 virus causing Covid-19. Unlike the understanding of the etiology and subsequent process of prophylactic measures against the polio virus (Rozsypal, 2019), scientific and medical authorities were faced with the task of determining prophylactic protocols for Covid-19 at the beginning. Various scientific teams attempted to find effective solutions, with vaccination emerging as one of the most efficient options. However, alongside the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, unfounded and false information began to circulate, which was also negative towards Covid-19 vaccination itself (Chowdhury et al., 2023; Schwle et al., 2022). The dissemination of unfounded beliefs related to Covid-19 was fueled by various anti-vaccine movements, which vehemently opposed vaccination, emphasizing alleged negative side effects that outweighed the benefits of vaccination (Burki, 2020; Mylan & Hardman, 2021). Furthermore, there was a general distrust of pharmaceutical companies and government institutions (Lanyi et al., 2022; Roberts et al., 2022). Despite the relative prevalence of unfounded beliefs and distrust, as was shown in our study, the willingness to recommend vaccination against Covid-19 could be influenced by brief pro-vaccination arguments, although their effect was not large. Along with the results of studies conducted previously that tested the effectiveness of similar interventions on reducing the unfounded beliefs and increase vaccination intentions (e.g. Jolley & Douglas, 2014), this seems to indicate that anti-vaccination beliefs and intentions can be changed to some extent and perhaps may not be as deep-rooted as they are sometimes believed to be (Holford et al., 2023).

Lastly, the differences between the groups in the level of trust in doctors were not confirmed, which can be interpreted against the backdrop of findings that trust in the healthcare system remained relatively stable in Slovakia, where our study was conducted, during the pandemic (SAV, 2021). According to the results of the mentioned research (available at SASD, 2021), up to 52% of respondents consider their doctor a trustworthy source of information,

including regarding vaccination. The experimental procedure recorded an effect of increased trust in scientists, but only between the control and the second experimental group. It seems that the additional information provided to the second experimental group, compared to the first experimental group, may have influenced this effect, although it was weak. This information pertained to the motives and fallacies in the thinking of those who spread unsubstantiated beliefs about vaccination. However, there was no difference between the groups once we accounted for the additional covariates in ANCOVA and therefore, this result should be interpreted with caution.

In conclusion, the results of the experimental study indicate that it is possible to reduce trust in COVID-19 unfounded beliefs (specifically conspiracy beliefs and pseudoscientific beliefs related to measures) and increase willingness to recommend vaccination against COVID-19 through arguments. These arguments consist of information that debunks false information and highlights the motives and fallacies in the thinking of those who share them. These findings demonstrate the prophylactic potential of the procedure, which could be utilized in future intervention programs in combination with the development of scientific thinking (Lieskovský & Sunyík, 2022). Following this line of research, in the future, it might be interesting to employ a longitudinal study where it would be possible to track the temporal effect of inoculation (regarding various diseases) on susceptibility to unfounded beliefs, as well as trust in scientific and medical authorities, along with the willingness to recommend vaccination in general. Crucially, it would also be important to estimate the longevity of the intervention effects, which remains questionable given the current research design. Alternative future direction may lie in testing more engaging and gamified forms of interventions. Indeed, some studies show that effective prebunking and debunking of misinformation (related to Covid-19 as well as more generic fake news) can take form of relatively brief online games (Basol et al., 2020; 2021) that have the potential to affect a wide audience in a short time. Indeed, such gamified prebunking and debunking interventions against unfounded beliefs may have the potential to increase participants' engagement with the intervention and thus produce stronger and longer-lasting effects when it comes to reducing the endorsement of unfounded beliefs. Nevertheless, we believe that demonstrating the robust effect of brief argument-based interventions on reducing popular unfounded beliefs about Covid-19 and increasing vaccination intentions while accounting for a range of covariates measured in the present study provides a valuable addition to research on countering anti-vaccination attitudes and intentions.

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